

TASKS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH OF PRODUCTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE OF SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article illustrates the improvement of the ecological culture of the population and society is possible due to the effective introduction of a system of continuous environmental education in our country. The fact is that without the formation of ecological consciousness and culture among the population, primarily among pupils and students studying in the system of continuing education, it is impossible to solve problems with any means spent on ecology and environmental protection.

Keywords: environmentally friendly, environmental knowledge, mandatory knowledge, ecological culture, ecological consciousness, nature, globalization.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the development of the ecological culture of children is one of the priorities of modern school education. The current approach to the formation and development of the ecological culture of future generation is going through a difficult path of its formation, during which the content, goals and objectives of pedagogical activity begin to change, while preserving, which is important, its essence, namely, the upbringing of harmoniously developed human relations and the environment of his habitat. However, the activity of our society is still capable of causing irreparable changes to nature, thereby confirming the fact that the level of ecological culture of the population remains insufficient. As a result, today it is necessary to search for relevant new approaches in order to progressively solve the problems of developing ecological culture among pupils. Formation and development of ecological culture among pupils which is one of the most significant tasks of improving the interaction of our society and nature. However, all these approaches should concern not only the teaching methods of individual scientific disciplines and the education of school children, but also the entire educational process of future teachers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An innovative view of the ongoing process of professional training of students from an environmental point of view is required. During the study of the processes under consideration, we have developed in detail a new spatial-ecological approach to solve this problem. Initially, it should be noted that one of the important tasks of the formation of ecological culture of school and under school children is the organization of educational research works on the theory and practice of professional teaching of ecology, ecologization of consciousness and behavior. In this regard, many scientists, including scientists of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are looking for the most optimal and rational principles, methods, forms and means of the learning process that can ensure its effective effectiveness. In addition, an important scientific problem is the search for an answer to the question of what, in essence, is ecological culture and environmental education, because, as you know, many people associate the formation of ecological culture with environmental education. In this regard, we need to note that the modern tasks of environmental education in school education should be the development of pupils'

real understanding of man as an integral part of our nature, as well as the unity and self-worth of all living organisms with the impossibility of human survival without preserving our biosphere with the necessary reserve of ecological diversity. It is also necessary to competently teach school pupils the real perception of phenomena that are associated with people's lives in the natural environment, taking into account their professional activities. The tasks of school education also include full familiarization of pupils' with innovative and promising technologies that are "environmentally friendly", waste-free and resource-saving.

At the same time, the content of environmental education should be integrated and complex in nature, as well as include ideological, scientific-theoretical, practical, spiritual-moral, ethical, aesthetic, personal-worldview, legal and educational aspects.

As a result, environmental education should be a continuous process that takes place in the life of every person. Environmental education has both local and global changes that are developing in the present and future. Environmental education also involves the development of special feelings, consciousness, critical thinking, understanding, as well as skills for solving environmental problems, which will certainly contribute to the personal development of a person. The most important feature for environmental education in secondary specialized and higher institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the need to

integrate the existing educational space, which will combine the research potential of the humanities, natural sciences and technical sciences.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Thus, we decided to put forward the development and implementation of such an up-to-date content of environmental education, as a result of which it would allow us to answer the age-old question: "Why should we teach?", which would lead pupils to the necessary search for answers to new global questions: "Where and how to apply the knowledge gained?", "What should each person do for the sake of a universal future?". For such a purpose, teachers should introduce and adjust many essential aspects into the content of environmental education, allowing the following:– to teach pupils to correctly perceive the received information about the state of their natural environment with the ability to correctly interpret its consequences;

– to make the subject-specific ecological concept "environment" accessible, understandable and meaningful for each pupils;

– to teach pupils to perceive environmental problems as particularly significant and personally significant;

– try to change pupils' value orientations so that they cannot contradict sociocultural norms.

In the course of our research, a large-scale development of one of the most important aspects of the problem of environmental training of future generation was also carried out, namely, the system of forming the readiness of pupils for compulsory extracurricular work. At the same time, the formation of pupils' readiness for their ecological and pedagogical extracurricular activities is associated with the optimal implementation of the pedagogical orientation, where the development of professionally significant personality qualities, professional competence are the main activities of teachers.

SUMMARY

The formation of the proposed personality qualities lies as fundamental in the professional and pedagogical approach to the personality of the future generation, which should be applied regularly.

It is also necessary to take into account the importance of continuity and continuity of secondary special education with school and even higher education in the preparation of young professionals, with the mandatory inclusion of graduates to independent life, and realizing himself as a full-fledged person, citizen, family member, professional specialist.

Also, one of the main criteria for diagnosing the formation of the system of training pupils to conduct extracurricular activities for the formation and development of ecological culture should be the achievement by young teachers of a higher and strategic level of pedagogical activity. After all, almost any activity can imply the presence of its subjects with the inclusion of both the goal and the means, as well as the transformation process itself with its expected result. As a result, the formation and development of the ecological culture of pupils may depend on certain requirements and tasks for the ecological and pedagogical activity of the future teacher, as well as the degree of professional formation and the availability of conditions for the full implementation of educational activities.

References:

1. Nazirovich A.U. Intercultural communication in teaching foreign languages //International Journal Of Literature And Languages. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 05. – С. 16-21.
2. Abduqodirov U. N. Intercultural challenges in teaching foreign languages //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 11. – С. 201-206.
3. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2020). Technologies of developing the ecological culture of students in the process of learning a foreign languages in higher educational institutions. Solid State Technology, 63(1s), 1816-1825.
4. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. Central asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture, 2(12), 37-43.
5. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. Общество и инновации, 2 (10/S), 251-256.
6. Shulzhenko A.K. Education of aesthetic perception of the environment in European countries // Environmental education. 2005. No. 2. – p. 30.

